

Stay-at-Home Education and Engagement with NOIRLab

Constance E. Walker, Carolina Vargas, Peter Michaud

Screen shot from the first episode of Science@Home where students made Pocket Solar Systems in an activity led by Rob Sparks in Tucson.

Owing to ongoing concerns about COVID-19, all public, in-person NOIRLab engagement activities have been canceled or postponed until social distancing restrictions are no longer required. In response to the pandemic and the resulting challenges for parents, teachers, and students, NOIRLab's Communications, Education and Engagement

(CEE) group has initiated a Virtual Programming initiative with a range of resources aimed at stay-at-home learners and the interested public. Planned programming ranges from live video events to pre-recorded video and social media content highlighting NOIRLab's people, science, and technology. It is anticipated that virtual learning will have

an expanded and permanent place in our education and engagement programming long after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Recently, families of NOIRLab staff participated in a pilot project called Science@Home. Participants in the first session held in early April enjoyed an activity called Solar System in Your Pocket followed by a session on becoming a citizen scientist by taking night sky brightness measurements with the Globe at Night (www.globeatnight.org)

application. Additional Science@Home topics covered Moon phases and making a home-made gravity well. Currently, with schools out for the Tucson summer, Science@Home is on hiatus and expected to evolve into a program based on virtual Project ASTRO programming.

Another live NOIRLab program stems from the long-running Live from Gemini (www.gemini.edu/node/132) video “field trips.” Versions are offered in English (Live from NOIRLab @ Gemini) and Spanish (En Vivo desde NOIR-Lab). During these programs, students (K-12 through Astro 101) and public participants are introduced to the operation of a modern astronomical observatory, the technology that makes our research possible, and highlights from exciting recent discoveries. Each program includes a guest scientist or other staff who share their work in research or technology. Programs are archived on the NOIRLab YouTube channel at www.youtube.com/channel/UC6doHJLYMtAbJIEIQDB4Bdw

Of course, NOIRLab social media (www.facebook.com/NOIRLabAstro/photos) is an important component of virtual learning and engagement, and the CEE team is developing a minimum of two posts per week in Spanish and English that engage audiences in NOIRLab science, technology, people, and history. Also, check out recent “What’s Up in the Sky” Facebook video posts (www.facebook.com/pg/NOIRLabAstro/videos). Additionally, in Hawai‘i, the MKO@Home (www.hawaii.edu/news/2020/04/06/maunakea-observatories-at-home/) project is a joint effort by Gemini and all of the Maunakea Observatories. MKO@Home delivers a wide variety of weekly videos featuring astronomy-related activities, demonstrations, and interviews designed to encourage K-12 students and families to explore the Universe from home.

Watch NOIRLab social media pages (www.facebook.com/NOIRLabAstro) for details on upcoming programs for your families and friends!